

**Nutritional profiling of four edible orthopteran insects:
An alternate protein source for nutritional security in North East India**

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Abstract

Analytical studies were carried out to study the nutritional profile of four commonly consumed edible orthopteran insect species of Northeast India viz., field cricket (*Brachytrupes portentosus*), mole cricket (*Gryllotalpa africana*), rice grasshopper (*Oxya hyla*) and long horn grasshopper (*Ruspolia nitidula*) based on their proximate & elemental contents, amino & fatty acid profiles, and antioxidant properties.. The insects were also examined for their anti-nutritional factors and presence of any pathogenic microbes. The result of the proximate analysis revealed higher amount of crude protein (45.89-69.59%) as compared to other parameters like carbohydrate (5.13-24.21%), crude fat (8.47-37.61%), and crude fibre (2.89-9.13%) in all four studied species. Altogether 8 minerals were also estimated in considerable amounts. Amino acid profiling of all four species revealed the presence of 19 common amino acids, out of which 8 were essential. Quantification of the fatty acid profile revealed the presence of one essential omega 6 fatty acid *i.e.* linoleic acid (1.65%) in *O. hyla*. Antioxidant property associated with the nutritional eminence of edible insects was estimated in terms of Phenol (1.062-4.467 mg catechol equivalent/g) and flavonoid (2.412-4.470 mg quercetin equivalent/g) contents. Antinutritional factors *viz.* tannin, phytic acid and oxalic acid contents were recorded within the permissible limit (250-500 mg/100g). Furthermore, microbial analysis confirmed that these insects are free of food borne pathogenic microbes *i.e.* *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* sp. The present study vividly indicated that all the four species of edible insects are source of high-quality protein and stands out as a potential contributor to food security and sustainability throughout north east India where entomophagy is widely practiced.

